

D2.2 – Details of Test Methodology and Validation Plan

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Summary Sheet

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ACRONYMS

NEMO - NExt-generation **MO**dels for advanced battery electronics

EIS - Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

BLE - Bluetooth Low Energy

BESS - Battery Energy Storage System

BEV - Battery Electric Vehicle

PHEV - Plug-In Hybrid Electric Vehicle

HEV - Hybrid Electric Vehicle

AFE - Analog Front End

CPU - Central Processing Unit

RUL - Remaining Useful Life

SoX - State of X, summarize all kind of states e.g.: health or energy

SoC - State of Charge

SoH - State of Health

SoE - State of Energy

SoF - State of Function

SoP - State of Power

SoS - State of Safety

MSM - Mechanical Swelling Model

P-ECM - Physical Equivalent Circuit Model

P2D - Pseudo Two Dimensional

SotA - State of the Art

TR - Thermal Runaway

MAPE - Maximum Absolute Percentage Error

DRT - Distribution of Relaxation Times

BMS - Battery Management System

BMC - Battery Management Controller

SEI - Solid Electrolyte Interphase
CMC - Cell Measurement Controller
CMS - Cell Management System
DoD - Depth of Discharge
UART - Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter
I2C - Inter Integrated Circuit
SPI - Serial Peripheral Interface
CAN - Controller Area Network
API - Application Programming Interface
NTC - Negative Temperature Coefficient
FEC - Full Equivalent Cycles
OCV - Open Circuit Voltage
CC-CV - Constant Current - Constant Voltage
CC - Constant Current
WLTC - Worldwide Harmonized Light-Duty Vehicles Test Cycles
DST - Dynamic Stress Testing
EVB - Electric Vehicle Battery
KPI - Key Performance Indicator
EOL - End of Life
GITT - Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique
PNGV HPPC - Partnership for New Generation Vehicles Hybrid Pulse Power Characterization Method
HPPC - Hybrid Pulse Power Characterization

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	6
2. Partners' Contributions	7
3. Introduction	8
4. Methodology	10
5. Test Methodology and Validation Plan	11
5.1 Definitions and Reference Measurement Methods	11
5.1.1. SoC – State of Charge.....	11
5.1.2. SoH – State of Health	11
5.1.3. SoE – State of Energy	11
5.1.4. SoP – State of Power	11
5.1.5. SoS – State of Safety	12
5.1.6. RUL – Remaining Useful Life.....	12
5.1.7. Cell surface temperature	13
5.1.8. Core cell temperature	13
5.2 Battery Model Parameter Identification.....	13
5.2.1 P2D.....	14
5.2.2 MSM	15
5.2.3 P-ECM	15
5.2.4 RUL	16
5.2.5 SoS.....	16
5.3 Model Comparison	17
5.4 Validation	18
5.4.1 Hardware	18
5.4.2 zBMS	19
5.4.3 zMBS+	20
5.4.4 SoS.....	20
5.4.5 Cloud	22
6. Conclusions	23
7. Deviations	24
8. References	25

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.2, “Details of test methodology and validation plan”, is dedicated to the definition of the target studies. This includes the technical details of the testing methodology, covering all scheduled laboratory measurements and investigations, spanning from the characterization of individual cells to the cycling of cells and the two prototypes, the zBMS and zBMS+. The work also encompasses the definition of suitable cycling profiles, boundary conditions, and the definition of pass-fail criteria with respect to the specifications from deliverable D2.1. This deliverable report includes the design of experiments and details of the test methodologies for single battery cells and the developed module prototypes.

By delivering the D2.2 report, milestone M1 “Validation plan ready” is achieved: D2.2 is available and contains all required elements to verify the main project objective.

2. Partners' Contributions

Partner institution	Sections	Description of the contribution
IFAT	All	Drafting the deliverable
VUB, CSEM, TUG	All	Review
VUB	All	Final check

3. Introduction

The main objective of the NEMO project is to advance state-of-the-art battery management systems (BMS) by employing advanced physics-based and data-driven battery models and state estimators. These models and estimators rely on a wide range of sensor information, including battery cell impedance data from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), acquired at high data rates.

Deliverable 2.1 specified the use cases, the usage requirements, and the prototype specifications. Specifications were defined for both the hardware and the software level of the prototype battery management system.

Deliverable 2.2 focuses on defining the target studies, providing technical details for the battery testing methodologies and defining suitable battery cycling profiles. Furthermore, methodologies to validate and demonstrate the specified hardware and software requirements are defined.

The improved performance of the developed battery management systems will be demonstrated with the zBMS and zBMS+ platforms. The models and algorithms from WP3 and WP4 will be used for battery state estimation. The model's battery state estimation accuracies will be quantified and compared with a benchmark system according to the defined test methodology in WP7. Feedback of the obtained testing results allows for fine-tuning of the model parameters from WP3 and WP4. The functionality of the state of safety (SoS) estimation, prediction, and early failure detection will be demonstrated for the specified boundary conditions.

In WP7, the scheduled laboratory measurements with the zBMS and zBMS+ systems will be performed according to the defined test methodology and validation plan from task T2.3. Validation tests with the zBMS aim to demonstrate the improvement of the state of charge (SoC) and state of health (SoH) estimation accuracy within the updated BESTIMATOR™ framework, including models from T3.1, T3.2, and T3.3, by automatic model updates. Lifetime extension via active balancing in combination with ageing models developed in T3.1, T4.1, T4.2, and T4.3 will be demonstrated on the zBMS+ system. The zBMS module will be used as a benchmark system herein. Safety-related functionalities, such as the SoS estimation and early failure detection, will be demonstrated under laboratory conditions in a safe environment with single battery cells. Single batteries will be characterized, cycled and damaged intentionally (e.g. by mechanical indentation) and the evolution of the SoS indicators will be tracked.

In task T7.2, the test data acquired in T7.1 will be evaluated and used to validate the stated key performance indicators (KPIs). The developed algorithms and models' performance will be quantified in terms of systems improvement.

All tests will be performed according to the test methodologies defined in D2.2.

The **objectives** of D2.2 are to define:

- The test cases of the zBMS and zBMS+ demonstrators

- The verification of the hardware and software requirements
- The verification of the objectives and key performance indicators (KPIs)
- Validation to demonstrate KPIs

The **KPIs** relevant for D2.2 are:

- State of charge (SoC) maximum absolute percentage error (MAPE) below 1.0% after 18 months
- State of health (SoH) MAPE below 1%
- Remaining useful life (RUL) MAPE below 3%
- Module level lifetime extension of 20% at 80% of the remaining capacity
- Cell failure and thermal runaway (TR) events can be detected with an accuracy of 100% for the defined failure modes and triggers

Deliverable **inputs**:

To create deliverable D2.2, we have collaborated in several meetings, where all the partners have provided their input. Based on these inputs, we have defined the verification approach for the demonstrator.

Main Results:

The primary focus of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive test and verification concept for the two developed demonstrators, the zBMS and the zBMS+ platform. This deliverable specifies the performance checks of the algorithms and clearly defines the reference systems used to validate the test results.

4. Methodology

Requirements engineering is getting more and more important since the implementation of the standard ISO26262, and since the systems are getting more and more complex. Without proper requirements engineering a complete verification and validation of complex systems might not be possible.

Several tools for collecting, linking and deriving requirements are available. In the project NEMO, the consortium decided to use Sphinx-Needs as tool, which allows to create, manage, and analyze requirements, specifications, and test cases.

The consortium decided to use Gitlab as version control system to track the changes of requirements and build the report.

The following methodology is used for capturing test requirements according to the defined system and demonstrator requirements. Starting from the project objectives, the root requirements were derived and translated into user stories. A user story explains a function, a feature or a property of the system with only one or two sentences from the customer's point of view (who wants what and what for). This was done in Chapter 1 of the Annex of deliverable D2.1. All functional and parametric requirements are then derived from the user stories. Functional requirements describe what a system must do, while parametric requirements describe how well it must do it. This was done in deliverable D2.1 as well. The verification requirements for each functional and parametric requirement are specified in this report.

5. Test Methodology and Validation Plan

5.1 Definitions and Reference Measurement Methods

The BMS measures the battery cell current, the battery cell voltages, the battery cell temperatures, and the impedance of the battery cells. This data is then utilized as an input to a model, which estimates the battery cell's state of X (SoX). To verify the accuracy of the SoX estimation, reference measurements are taken using calibrated laboratory equipment. By comparing the SoX values generated by the model based on the BMS data with the values of the reference measurements, the BMS's performance can be evaluated. This section defines all SoX terms and the corresponding reference measurement methods.

5.1.1. SoC – State of Charge

The SoC can be described as the level of charge of a battery relative to its capacity. The units of SoC are percentage points and it is calculated as the ratio between the remaining energy in the battery at a given time $Q_{remaining}(t)$ and the maximum possible energy $Q_{max}(t)$ with the same SoH conditions.

$$SOC(t) = Q_{remaining}(t)/Q_{max}(t) * 100$$

5.1.2. SoH – State of Health

The estimation of the maximum level of charge of a battery relative to its initial value when it is first used is called SoH. The units of SoH are percentage points and it is calculated as the ratio between the maximum energy storing capacity in the battery at a given time $Q_{act}(t)$ and the maximum energy Q_{nomial} was able to store initially (nominal capacity).

$$SOH(t) = Q_{act}(t)/Q_{nomial} * 100$$

Coulomb counting with calibrated laboratory equipment is used to determine the reference SoH on cell and module levels and for different operating temperatures. The SoH of the battery is determined by a capacity check consisting of three full charge-discharge cycles, constant current - constant voltage (CC-CV) - constant current (CC) with a C/3 rate (C refers to the rated current). The 3rd discharge capacity is considered the actual capacity ($Q_{act}(t)$).

5.1.3. SoE – State of Energy

SoE is a synonym for SoH.

5.1.4. SoP – State of Power

A battery's SoP is defined as the ratio of peak power to nominal power. The peak power, based on present battery cell or module conditions, is the maximum power that may be

maintained constant for T seconds without violating preset operational design limits on battery voltage, SoC, power, or current.

$$SOP(t) = P_{max}(t)/P_{nomial} * 100$$

SOP cannot be directly measured and is affected by various factors such as ambient temperature, operating condition, and SoC [1]. For high precision SoP estimation, establishing a precise battery model and accurately identifying the model parameters are required. Most available SoP estimations rely on an equivalent circuit model, and the main difference lies in the type of equivalent circuit model and parameter identification method. The earliest and simplest SoP estimation method is the Partnership for New Generation Vehicles hybrid pulse power characterization method (PNGV HPPC). Calibrated laboratory equipment is used to determine the reference SoP on cell and module level and for different operating temperatures.

5.1.5. SoS – State of Safety

A battery's SoS describes the tolerable load of the battery cell until failure occurs. Failure is reached when an internal short circuit or thermal runaway is triggered. The abusive load will be applied in the form of mechanical or thermal loads. An internal short circuit will be detected for a voltage drop of 0.05 V according to [2].

Abuse tests with mechanical and thermal abusive loads will be performed under laboratory conditions to derive the tolerable load (voltage, temperature and impedance threshold). These thresholds are the basis for the short-term SoS estimation and long-term SoS prediction.

5.1.6. RUL – Remaining Useful Life

The remaining useful life is defined as the service life in terms of the number of full equivalent cycles left until the battery reaches its end of life (EoL). Long-term cycling protocols are to be performed on cells, zBMS and zBMS+ at room temperature. Cell level aging tests will include a full range of cycle and calendar life conditions while the automotive reference of 75-80% SoH operating window could be selected for module cycling test. Recommended C-rate capacity test, internal resistance measurement with pulse test and a full range frequency-based impedance check will be performed for the SoH tracking. The RUL of the batteries will be determined by predicting the whole lifetime and following the below equation and could be expressed in terms of number of cycles or time remaining in the service life.

$$RUL = Lifetime (EoL) - SoH$$

The aging tests will be performed on fresh batteries considering the 70% SoH as the EoL.

5.1.7. Cell surface temperature

The cell surface temperature is measured via negative temperature coefficient (NTC) sensors. The NTC sensors will be applied in the middle of the cell for single cell testing with the placement of additional sensors in the area of the tabs or on other positions of the cell (e.g. side of the cell) as needed. Depending on the test setup (e.g. preloaded cell) the position of the temperature sensor might be varied and will be documented accordingly. For the zBMS the temperature sensors will be placed at cell connectors. For the zBMS+ the temperature sensors will be placed by CSEM.

5.1.8. Core cell temperature

The cell core temperature is the temperature of the active material of the jelly roll inside the battery cell. The cell core temperature is understood of an average temperature value among the different materials (e.g., anode, cathode and electrolyte) as well as throughout the entire surface of anode-cathode interface. At first approximation we assume that the core temperature is homogeneous across materials and the entire active material surface, although it is understood that local differences apply in reality.

The reference measurement to the determination of the cell core temperature is established via the integration of the temperature sensors inside the cell under evaluation (e.g. cells are cut open on top in a glove box, the sensor is introduced in the middle of the jelly roll, hole is sealed). Different temperature sensors like e.g. NTC, optical or similar sensors are available, where optical (e.g. Bragg-based) sensors can sense temperature along the entire sensor, e.g. every 1 cm. Therefore, optical sensors can be used to sample the one or eventually two-dimensional core temperature distribution.

In the frame of the project the temperature dependence of the resistance of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer will be exploited in order to estimate the cell core temperature. The temperature coefficient of SEI layer resistance will be determined via lab measurement and the actual resistance of the SEI layer will be determined continuously via in-operando EIS measurements, which in the end will allow to determine a cell core temperature estimate.

5.2 Battery Model Parameter Identification

Within the NEMO project, five different models are used for battery state estimation:

- P2D – Pseudo Two-Dimensional Model
- MSM – Mechanical Swelling Model
- P-ECM – Physical Equivalent Circuit Model
- RUL – Remaining Useful Life Model
- SoS – State of Safety Model

All models, including their inputs and outputs, are defined in Chapter 5 of the Annex of deliverable D2.1.

Parameter identification is the process of estimating the values of the parameters that define a mathematical model to best match experimental data. After defining a mathematical model, experimental data is collected. This dataset includes measurements of the system's input and output variables. An optimization algorithm then estimates the values of the model parameters that best match the measured experimental data.

This section describes which system variables have to be measured for which model and under which boundary conditions.

To facilitate model parameter identification, electrical tests on single battery cells are carried out across a range of operational scenarios. The following electrical characteristics need to be determined continuously for model parameterization:

- Cell voltage
- Cell current
- SoC
- SoH
- SoP
- Cell surface temperature
- Cell core temperature
- EIS

EIS characterization is performed for the following parameter space:

- SoC from 0% to 100% in 5% steps
- Temperature from -40°C to 50°C in 10°C steps
- Measurement frequency from 20 mHz to 1 kHz with 6 measurements per decade
- Excitation current amplitude set to min. 0.5% and max. 5% of nominal cell capacity

5.2.1 P2D

The parameters of the P2D model can be categorized into 3 categories: electrode parameters, electrolyte parameters and separator parameters. The basic parameters are:

- Reaction rate constants
- Diffusion coefficient of Lithium-ion
- Ionic conductivity of the electrolyte
- Electronic conductivity of the electrodes
- SEI layer resistance

These will be collected from literature data and existing data within the modeling environment. However, to facilitate parameter identification and model validation, electrochemical tests of a single current profile including constant current - constant voltage (CC-CV), EIS and driving cycling profile will be carried out across a range of operational scenarios. This data will be generated as parts of 5.1.4 and 5.1.5.

5.2.2 MSM

The mechanical characterization is the basis for the MSM. Mechanical properties are derived by mechanical abusive tests. The MSM is calibrated by compression experiments and continuous measurement of EIS. The MSM is validated by single cell cycling experiments with different preload forces applied.

Mechanical abuse test (0% SoC) to derive mechanical stiffness

- Output: Force-displacement, voltage-displacement, temperature-time
- Single cell experiment without BMS measurement (without zBMS): Fresh, Aged
- Measurement testbed: Force, displacement, temperature
- Measurement BMS: none
- Tested SoC: 0%
- Mechanical load: local indentation, < 1mm/s
- Temperature: $T = 20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (no temperature control)
- Abort condition: maximum force 420 kN

Cycling with preload: Apply preload force and vary SoC to find correlation with EIS

- Output: Swelling vs. force, EIS vs. force, EIS vs. swelling
- Single cell experiment with BMS measurement (zBMS): Fresh, Aged
- Measurement testbed: Force, displacement, temperature, current, voltage
- Measurement BMS: Current, voltage, EIS
- SoC range: 0 to 100%
- Preload force: Flat compression, 0 N and 2 different levels
- Temperature: $T = 20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (no temperature control)
- Abort condition: maximum force 20 kN, temperature $> 60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

5.2.3 P-ECM

The P-ECM model will be determined in at least three cells that will be integrated into the zBMS and zBMS+ demonstrators. For the initial determination of the P-ECM model parameters the EIS characterization in the following parameter space will be covered:

- Open circuit voltage (OCV) tests with C/20 charge and discharge current
- Relaxation test based on galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) protocol with 0.5% and 5% of nominal cell capacity and timing adapted to the cell specifications
- SoC values: 0%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%
- Temperature values: $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Measurement frequency from 10 mHz to 10 kHz with 10 measurements per decade
Excitation current amplitude set to 0.5% and 5% of the nominal cell capacity

5.2.4 RUL

The lifetime characterization protocols will be based on stationary and automotive use cases where the following parameters will be varied as part of different cycling and storage conditions. The stress parameters can be categorized as the following which will be detailed before performing the experimental measurements.

Cycle life study:

- Depth of cycling: 10 to 100%
- State of charge range: 0 to 100%
- Temperature range: 5 °C to 45 °C
- Current amplitude (charge/discharge): 0.33C to 2C

Calendar life study:

- Storage state of charge: 20 to 100%
- Storage temperature range: 5 °C to 45 °C
- **Reference performance test (RPT):**
- Capacity checked as described in Section 5.1.2.
- Hybrid pulse power characterization (HPPC) test at three SoC points
- EIS test - Measurement frequency from 1 Hz to 10 kHz with 10 measurements per decade
- Excitation current amplitude set to 0.5% and 5% of the nominal cell capacity

The frequency of the reference performance test could be once every 100 full equivalent cycles (FEC)) while data acquisition at a 1 Hz rate would suffice. At certain intervals, a full range of frequencies (10 kHz to 5 mHz) could be performed with a dedicated potentiostat.

Data acquisition protocol:

- A minimum of 2 cells per condition is to be performed.
- Reference EIS tests and capacity check are to be performed at specified cycling, e.g., every 100 full equivalent cycles, and/or storage frequency.
- Data storage at 1Hz frequency should suffice.
- No mechanical pressure is to be imposed during the aging study.
- Temperature condition (excluding humidity) is to be maintained during tests.

5.2.5 SoS

Cell core temperature estimation is an integral part of the SoS model. For the determination of the associated model parameters, an EIS characterization will be carried out for all battery cells that will be used for the SoS model validations. The following parameter space will be covered for these tests:

- OCV tests with C/20 charge and discharge current

- Relaxation test based on GITT protocol with 0.5% and 5% of nominal cell capacity and timing adapted to the cell specifications
- SoC values: 0%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%
- Temperature values: -10°C, 10°C, 30°C and 50°C
- Measurement frequency from 1 Hz to 10 kHz with 10 measurements per decade
- Excitation current amplitude set to 0.5% and 5% of the nominal cell capacity
- Tests with and without load, e.g. worldwide harmonized light-duty vehicles test cycles (WLTC) profile, according to cell specifications

Safety-relevant electro-mechanical thresholds are defined by mechanical abuse tests and are the basis for the SoS definition. Critical deformations until short circuit and core-temperature are evaluated to define a SoS estimator. Single cell cycling of pre-damaged cells is used to generate validation data for the SoS and cell failure detection algorithm.

Abuse tests: Mechanical abuse test to derive critical battery parameters and trigger thermal runaway

- Output: Force-displacement, voltage-displacement, temperature-time, core-temperature-time, EIS
- Single cell experiment with BMS measurement (with zBMS): Fresh, Aged
- Measurement testbed: Force, displacement, temperature
- Measurement BMS: Current, voltage, EIS
- Tested SoC: > 60%
- Mechanical load: local indentation, < 1mm/s
- Temperature: 20°C (no temperature control)
- Abort condition: maximum force 420 kN

Cycling with pre-damaged cells: Single cell cycling with CC-CV charging and constant current (CC) discharging with non-critical pre-damage

- Output: Force vs. cycles, swelling vs. cycles, EIS vs. cycles
- Single cell experiment with BMS measurement (with zBMS)
- Measurement testbed: Force, displacement, temperature, current, voltage
- Measurement BMS: Current, voltage, EIS
- SoC range: 0 to 100%
- Preload force: Flat compression with local indenter, 0 N and 2 different levels
- Temperature: 20°C (no temperature control)
- Abort condition: maximum force 20 kN, temperature > 60°C, max cycle count

5.3 Model Comparison

All BMS data is available to the master but also stored in the cloud such that model and algorithm outputs can be always recomputed. The IAV models and algorithms that are currently available on the Aurix master are used as references, e.g. SoC and SoH models and algorithms.

1. IAV models and algorithms are running on Aurix master, results are transmitted to cloud. NEMO project models and algorithms are calculated based on cloud data (measurement) and associated SoX results are also stored in the cloud.
2. Comparisons are made for the local and NEMO models and algorithms based on cloud data.

5.4 Validation

The KPIs of the NEMO demonstrators, the zBMS and the zBMS+, are defined in Section 4 of deliverable D2.1 and are included in Section 3 of this document for the reader’s convenience. This section defines the validation process, including the methods used to test the demonstrator’s functionality, in order to show that the project’s KPIs are met.

5.4.1 Hardware

The concept of the system architecture of the zBMS and the zBMS+ platform is specified in Chapter 3 of the Annex of deliverable D2.1. The figures below depict schematic drawings of the two demonstrators.

Figure 1 - Conceptual schematic of zBMS.

Figure 2 - Conceptual schematic of zBMS+.

The top-level functionality of the hardware will be validated by connectivity tests for data transfer and by plausibility checks of measurement values with and without charge/discharge current at the end of assembly process. This includes:

- Cell voltage measurement
- Cell temperature measurement
- EIS
- Battery pack current
- Battery pack voltage
- Data transfer to the main controller (wired / wireless) and the cloud
- Control of balancing switches
- Control of contactor and precharge

BMS calibration procedure: Measurement results of the BMS will be compared with the measurement results of calibrated laboratory equipment at the testbench which shall be used for module aging. This has to be done before further evaluation of modules.

5.4.2 zBMS

The validation of OBJ2 and OBJ3 will be carried out on the zBMS module. This module will be cycled and aged over 18 months based on the following protocol:

- Standard discharge from 90% SoC down to 10% SoC based on WLTC or Formula-E driving cycle¹ and at room temperature (typically between 20°C and 30°C).
- Standard recharge from 10% SoC to 90% SoC with C/5 CC phase and final CV phase.
- A relaxation time of 2h hours is foreseen between standard charge and discharge cycles after each recharge.

¹ 1h to 3h active discharge cycles will be implemented, which are followed by about 1h resting cycles. Such a structure is representative for automotive driving cycles and also provides the necessary resting times to regularly update the P-ECM model parameters across the entire SoC range from time to time.

- Extension to full SoC range (from 0% to 100%) every 10 standard charge/recharge cycles for two full discharge cycles, where the recharge is in fast charging mode, e.g. CC-phase with 2C (check with cell specs); second fast charge up to 90% SoC.
- A reference EIS acquisition will be taken from time to time during the relaxation phases, where one cell of the module will be instrumented to run an EIS with reference laboratory equipment, e.g. a Gamry potentiostat.

For these tests, the ground truth SoH will be determined according to the reference method described in Section 5.1.2. The values for SoC and SoH determined by the NEMO algorithms will be determined based on local measurements that are going to be calculated in the cloud. The reference SoC and SoH values from the IAV reference algorithms will be determined based on the same data, but these values will be calculated directly on the BMS master (see also Section 5.6 below). The initial values for the P-ECM will be determined from the lab measurements described in Section 5.2. The model parameters will then be updated regularly, e.g. EIS measurements at different SoC and temperature levels will be triggered by the BMS, the associated data will be stored in the cloud and the P-ECM parameters will be determined there. Two modules can be cycled in parallel.

Besides, the same above-mentioned cycling procedure on cell level and additional types will also be performed separately. The below steps are proposed:

- Static cycle life study at 30 °C with recommended C-rates and 80% depth of discharge (DoD) (15%-95% SoC).
- Standard drive cycle (adapted to cell level) such as worldwide harmonized light duty cycle profile (WLTC) at 30 °C and with a maximum 70% DoD (20%-90% SoC). The cycling procedure may include a 2-day rest at room temperature at 50% SoC.
- Reference performance test as mentioned in Sections 5.1.2 and 5.1.6 for SoH and RUL tracking.

5.4.3 zMBS+

The validation of OBJ4 will be carried out on the zBMS+ module. This module will be cycled and aged over 12 months based on the same cycling protocol as outlined above in Section 5.4.2. The zBMS+ modules integrate the SoH balancing option, which will be controlled by the BMS. The ageing performance of the zBMS+ modules will be compared to the ageing performance of the zBMS modules, e.g., the SoH after 12 months of cycling will be compared and the associated lifetime extension will be calculated based on a linear extrapolation of the cycle count. Two modules can be cycled in parallel.

5.4.4 SoS

Single cell tests will be performed in order to validate OBJ5 (MSM, short-term and long-term SoS algorithm) and will be carried out on single cell level.

Validation of MSM: Single cell cycling (CCCV charging, CC discharging) with preload force and mapping of preload force and thickness (swelling) evolution

- Output: Force vs. cycles, swelling vs. cycles, EIS vs. cycles
- Single cell experiment with BMS measurement (zBMS)

- Measurement testbed: Force, displacement (swelling), temperature, current, voltage
- Measurement BMS: Current, voltage, EIS
- Model output: swelling, force
- SoC range: 0 to 100%
- Preload force: Flat compression with 0 N and 2 different levels
- Temperature: $T = 20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (no temperature control)
- Abort condition: maximum force 20 kN, temperature $> 60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, max cycle count

Validation of short-term SoS: Mechanical abuse with different conditions than model calibration test

- Output: Force-displacement, voltage-displacement, temperature-time, core-temperature-time, EIS
- Single cell experiment with BMS measurement (with zBMS): Fresh, Aged
- Measurement testbed: Force, displacement, temperature
- Measurement BMS: Current, voltage, EIS
- Model output: Force, short-term SoS
- Tested SoC: $> 60\%$
- Mechanical load: Local indentation, $< 1\text{ mm/s}$
- Temperature: 20°C (no temperature control)
- Abort condition: maximum force 420 kN

Validation of short-term SoS with core-temperature: Single cell thermal abuse (heating) with integrated core temperature sensor

- Output: Derived core temperature vs. measured core temperature
- Single cell experiment with BMS measurement (with zBMS)
- Measurement BMS: surface temperature, current, voltage, EIS
- Measurement testbed: surface temperature, core-temperature, voltage
- Model output: derived core-temperature, short-term SoS
- Tested SoC: $> 60\%$
- External heating: $> 5^{\circ}\text{C/min}$
- Abort condition: none

Validation of long-term SoS: Cycling (CCCV charging, CC discharging) of pre-damaged single cell and mapping of long-term SoS

- Output: Force vs. cycles, swelling vs. cycles, EIS vs. cycles, long-term SoS
- Single cell experiment with BMS measurement (with zBMS)
- Measurement testbed: Force, displacement, temperature, current, voltage
- Measurement BMS: Current, voltage, EIS
- SoC range: 0 to 100%
- Preload force: Flat compression with local indenter, 0 N and 2 different levels
- Temperature: 20°C (no temperature control)
- Abort condition: maximum force 20 kN, temperature $> 60^{\circ}\text{C}$, max cycle count

5.4.5 Cloud

The validation of the cloud performance is measured by performing automated tests which check if all the data produced by the BMS is transmitted to the cloud and stored in the data base in the following manner:

- Timely (data should be stored in the cloud in less than 1 hour after measurement)
- Complete (no data should be lost in the transmission process)
- Without duplicates

6. Conclusions

The main objective of the NEMO project is to advance state-of-the-art BMS by employing advanced physics-based and data-driven battery models and state estimators. Deliverable 2.1 specified the use cases, the usage requirements, and the specifications of the prototype battery management systems, the zBMS and the zBMS+. This report, "Details of test methodology and validation plan", includes the design of experiments and details of the test methodologies for single battery cells and the developed module prototypes necessary for battery model development and demonstration and validation of the project's KPIs. This includes the definition of suitable cycling profiles, boundary conditions, and the definition of pass-fail criteria with respect to the hardware and software specifications from deliverable D2.1. All tests will be performed according to the test methodologies defined in this report.

The improved performance of the developed BMS will be demonstrated with the zBMS and zBMS+ platforms. The models and algorithms from WP3 and WP4 will be used for battery state estimation. The model's battery state estimation accuracies will be quantified and compared with a benchmark system according to the defined test methodology in WP7 to demonstrate the following KPIs:

- State of charge (SoC) maximum absolute percentage error (MAPE) below 1.0% after 18 months
- State of health (SoH) MAPE below 1%
- Remaining useful life (RUL) MAPE below 3%
- Module level lifetime extension of 20% at 80% of the remaining capacity
- Cell failure and thermal runaway (TR) events can be detected with an accuracy of 100% for the defined failure modes and triggers

By delivering the D2.2 report, milestone M1 "Validation plan ready" is achieved.

In summary, this deliverable provides a comprehensive test and verification concept for the two developed demonstrators, the zBMS and the zBMS+ platform. D2.2 specifies the performance checks of the algorithms and clearly defines the reference systems used to validate the test results.

7. Deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

8. References

[1] Plett et al., High-performance battery-pack power estimation using a dynamic cell model, 2004, IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, Vol. 53, No. 5, pp. 1586-1593, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2004.832408>

[2] Liu et al., Safety issues and mechanisms of lithium-ion battery cell upon mechanical abusive loading: A review, 2020, Energy Storage Materials, Vol. 25, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2019.06.036>